

Questionnaire for a survey on forms of evaluation of
oriented research proposals

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Latin American Forum for Research Assessment (FOLEC) of the Latin American Council of Social Sciences (CLACSO) and the International Development Research Centre (IDRC), Canada.

This questionnaire is inspired by the evaluation experience of the Sectorial Commission for Scientific Research (CSIC) of the University of the Republic, Uruguay. It has been designed by Natalia Gras, Associate Professor of the Academic Unit of the CSIC of the University of the Republic, Uruguay, within the framework of CLACSO-IDRC 109465-001 Project, based in CLACSO's research area, directed by Pablo Vommaro. It benefits from the participation of FOLEC-CLACSO (as an observer) in the research evaluation work group of the Global Research Council, in DORA's Advisory Council, and more recently in the scoping group on research assessment promoted by InterAcademy Partnership (IAP), the Global Young Academy (GYA) and the International Science Council (ISC); also from the collaboration of Prof. T.A. Abinandanan, Venkat Nadella and Poonam Pandey from DST-Centre for Policy Research (CPR), Indian Institute of Science (IISc) and the contribution of the work team made up of Laura Rovelli, Dominique Babini and Ana Luna González from FOLEC-CLACSO.

"Development problems" will be used to refer broadly to the problems of social and economic development of the countries (problems in the area of production of goods and services, public policy, health, social exclusion, poverty, environmental, energy, etc.).

Welcome

Information for participants and consent. The questionnaire takes an average of 20 to 25 minutes to complete it. **You can download a PDF version of the questionnaire for guidance here:**

<https://biblioteca-repositorio.clacso.edu.ar/bitstream/123456789/3337/1/EnglishVersion.Questionnaire.CLACSO.IDRCProject.pdf>

But only responses received by completing the online questionnaire will be processed.

You can find more information about the project [here](#).

What is this questionnaire about?

We intend, through this questionnaire, to gather information on the forms of evaluation of research proposals oriented to the search for solutions to development problems, their characteristics, processes and evaluation criteria by specialists and/or authorities of scientific and/or higher education organizations in countries of the **Global South**, with focus **on developing economies of South Asia: Bangladesh, India, and Sri Lanka.**

In this way, we aim to highlight and analyze relevant and quality ways of evaluating research proposals for funding to better adapt to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), global "grand challenges" and local critical situations, as well as to facilitate funding schemes that promote more inclusive research systems.

Our results will be open access and internationally disseminated to major funders of science, innovation and higher education.

Initiatives participating in this research will be selected to be invited to present their case at the [9th. Latin American and Caribbean Social Science Conference](#), to be held in Mexico City, Mexico, June 7-10, 2022.

Who can answer the questionnaire?

Specialists and/or authorities of the organization in charge of a call/instrument to finance research projects in some of the countries of the Global South, with focus on developing economies of **South Asia: Bangladesh, India, and Sri Lanka.**

It is possible to answer one form for the most representative call/instrument for the promotion of oriented research in your organisation; or two or more forms for each of the most relevant calls/instruments for the promotion of oriented research in your organisation.

How will my responses be used and stored?

The results of this questionnaire will be used in a CLACSO-IDRC study. The survey is personalized. Those who complete the questionnaire will be referenced as contributors to this research in the final report. However, their personal contact information will be used exclusively for the purposes of this research and will be kept strictly confidential. The controller of this project is CLACSO and the final results will be published in June 2022 in a CLACSO-IDRC report.

Contact

If you have any questions or concerns, please contact the project coordinator, Dr. Laura Rovelli, Coordinator of the Latin American Forum for Scientific Evaluation (FOLEC-CLACSO): folec@clacso.edu.ar.

1. Consent to participate

Please check the box below to indicate that you agree to participate in this study:

- I have read the participant information on the previous pages and understand the context of the research study.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the survey at any time, without having to give a reason, and without any consequences.

I understand that I am giving the research team the right to use and make available the information I share (even if it is not attributed to me and/or my organization, if indicated) without further consent in the following ways:

A) Publications in scholarly journals and other media; or talks at public conferences.

B) Reports, online media, blogs, policy briefs.

Disclaimer

CLACSO-IDRC is not responsible for the content of the questionnaires created through the SurveyMonkey service, or for the opinions expressed in them.

Yes

No

I. Contextual and program/calls/scheme characteristics

I.1 General characteristics of the organization

2. In which country is your organization located?

3. What is the name of your organization?

4. What type of organization is your organization? (Check the appropriate option)

- Public university
- Private university
- Public-private university
- International university
- National Research Center
- Regional Research Center
- International Research Center
- National Council of Science, Technology and Innovation
- Regional Council for Science, Technology and Innovation
- Ministry/Secretariat for Science, Technology and Innovation or other type of governmental entity with responsibility for the definition of Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) policies
- National Agency of Science, Technology and Innovation or other type of governmental entity with responsibility for the execution of public policies in STI
- Other (Specify)

5. Does your organization promote responsible evaluation of research?

- No
- Don't Know
- Yes (specify)

6. Does your organization support any of the existing statements, recommendations, or principles on responsible research evaluation? (Check all that apply)

- San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA; <https://sfdora.org>)
- Leiden Manifesto on Research Metrics (<http://www.leidenmanifesto.org>)
- Hong Kong Principles (<https://www.wcrif.org/guidance/hong-kong-principles>)
- Global Research Council's Statement of Principles on Peer Review and Merit (https://www.globalresearchcouncil.org/fileadmin/documents/GRC_Publications/Statement_of_Principles_on_Peer-Merit_Review_2018.pdf)
- Science Europe's Recommendations on Research Assessment Processes (<https://www.scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/research-assessment/>)
- Assessment framework developed by your own organization. If you have a link to such an evaluation framework, please copy it here:

7. Does your organization use another principles on responsible research evaluation?

8. Does your organization have a formal definition of research quality?

- No
- Don't know
- Yes (specify)

9. How much does your organization encourage and promote the following aspects in funding programs/calls/schemes?

	In all	In a few	Not encouraged
Ethics and integrity (of the research proposals, their research teams and of the people involved in the evaluation processes).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Social commitment and participation of society's stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Open access and open science	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Equity, diversity and inclusion of underrepresented groups.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consideration of balances with respect to certain aspects (geographic, institutional, thematic, gender, etc.) in the distribution of research resources.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Interdisciplinarity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

10. Which of the following statements about the assessment of targeted research proposals are implemented in your organization? (Please check all that apply)

In this questionnaire, "oriented research" refers synthetically to "research oriented to the search for solutions to development problems".

- (i) All units/departments in your organization follow the same processes to evaluate research proposals according to the same procedures.
- (ii) Your organization adapts the procedures for evaluating research proposals according to different fields of knowledge and/or when different research products are intended to be obtained.
- (iii) Your organization provides training for people involved in the evaluation of research proposals (reviewers, members of expert panels, etc.).
- (iv) Your organization provides written guidelines to persons involved in the evaluation of research proposals (reviewers, members of expert panels, etc.).
- (v) Your organization explicitly informs reviewers and/or members of expert panels of the tools and criteria that MUST NOT be used in the evaluation of research proposals.
- (vi) Your organization asks reviewers and/or panel members to complete a form specifically designed to address all aspects of the research proposal to be evaluated.

11. If you answered (iii) or (iv) in Question 10: What aspects does the training/guidelines consider for persons involved in the evaluation of targeted research proposals? (Check all that apply)

- Defining, identifying and dealing with conflicts of interest
- Tasks and roles to be performed
- Tools, metrics and criteria to be used in the evaluation of targeted research proposals
- Procedures and organization of the meetings of the panel of experts
- Ethical standards of behavior to ensure impartiality with respect to gender, race, disciplinary fields, organizations of affiliation of research proposals, and the seniority or academic leadership of the applicants.
- None of the above
- Other (Specify)

I.2 Characteristics

12. What is the name of the funding programs/calls/schemes for the promotion of targeted research?

I.2.1 Temporal aspects

13. When (year) was this program/call/scheme created?

14. How long does funding last? (Check the appropriate option)

- Up to one year
- More than one year and up to two years
- More than two years and up to three years
- More than three years and up to five years
- More than five years

15. Does this program/call/scheme has regular calls for proposals since its creation? (Check the appropriate option)

- Yes
- No
- Don't know
- Not applicable

16. How often do they call for proposals? (Check the appropriate option)

- Annual (every year)
- Biennial (every two years)
- Triennial (every three years)
- Quadrennial (every four years)
- Proposals for targeted research are received and evaluated as they arrive. There is no call for proposals, research proposals may be submitted at any time.
- Other (specify)

I.2.2 Financial aspects

17. Which research items can be financed with this program/call/scheme? (Check all that apply)

- Salaries of the investigators involved in the research proposal
- Salaries of support personnel (technical, administrative) for the implementation of the research proposal
- Expenditures on instruments, materials and inputs needed to carry out the research activities
- Investments in equipment and infrastructure
- Other (Specify)

18. What is the average and the maximum total amount- in current U.S. dollars- financed by this funding program/call/scheme per selected research proposal?

I.2.3 Responsible person for submitted proposals

19. Who can be responsible for the proposals submitted to the program/call/scheme? (Check the appropriate option)

In the options below, non-academic actors refer to companies, cooperatives, small rural producers, family producers, government public agencies (federal, state, municipal), government secretariats / ministries, non-governmental organizations, social and union organizations, hospitals , educational centers (initial, primary, secondary, technical, etc.).

- Academic actors only (researchers; research groups; research centers, public and private)
- Academic and non-academic actors of any kind (who contribute knowledge to the proposed research)
- Only non-academic actors (eventually incorporating researchers to the work team).

I.2.4 Cognitive aspects

20. Which discipline of knowledge - alone or in combination - may be involved in the oriented research proposals submitted to the program/call/scheme? (Please check all that apply)

- Arts
- Social Sciences
- Agricultural Sciences
- Medical and Health Sciences
- Natural and Exact Sciences
- Social Sciences
- Humanities
- Engineering and Technology
- Some combination of the above fields (please specify which)

21. Does this program/call/scheme delimit the problems or topics to which targeted research proposals should be addressed?

- Yes
- No

22. If you answered Yes to question 21, what methods does your organization use to identify and delimit the problems or topics to be addressed by the targeted research proposals submitted to the program/call/scheme? (Please check all that apply)

- Defined by Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)
- Defined by the development objectives of the region or continent
- Defined by the country's development priorities
- Exploring problems present in the territory or in specific organizations and identifying scientific and technological knowledge needs to address them.
- Organizing workshops/seminars with suppliers and demanders of knowledge on topics of interest
- Interviewing different actors in society
- Organizing workshops with specialists in topics of interest.
- Other (specify)

II. Evaluation Process

II.1 Aspects of the ex ante procedure

II.1.1 Evaluation systems implemented in your organization

23. What systems does your organization currently implement for the evaluation of targeted research proposals? (Please check all that apply)

- (i) Peer review - double-blind by experts/specialists external to your organization (external reviewers do not know the identity of the applicants and vice-versa)
- (ii) Peer review - double-blind conducted by experts/specialists internal to your organization (internal reviewers do not know the identity of the applicants and vice-versa)
- (iii) Peer review - single-blind conducted by experts/specialists external to your organization (external reviewers know the identity of the applicants, but the latter do not know who the reviewers are)
- (iv) Single-blind peer review conducted by experts/specialists internal to your organization (internal reviewers know the identity of the applicants, but the applicants do not know who the reviewers are).
- (v) Open reviews conducted by experts/specialists external to your organization (the identity of both external reviewers and reviewers is known to all).
- (vi) Open reviews by experts/specialists internal to your organization (the identity of both internal reviewers and nominators is known to all)
- (vii) Panel of external specialists discusses and reviews individual evaluation reports to classify research proposals as fundable or non-fundable.
- (viii) Internal peer review panel discusses and reviews individual evaluation reports to rank research proposals as fundable or non-fundable.
- (ix) Research proposals are evaluated, ranked and classified as fundable or non-fundable according to a set of quantitative criteria.
- (x) Other (specify)

II.1.2 Criteria for the integration of expert panels

24. If you answered (vii) or (viii) in Question 23, what are the criteria for the integration of the specialist panels? (Please check all that apply)

- Degree of experience and academic knowledge
- The degree of experience and knowledge in the practice of the development problems to be addressed by the research proposal.
- To ensure the disciplinary diversity of the composition of the panels of specialists
- To ensure institutional diversity in the composition of the panels of specialists.
- To guarantee gender parity in the composition of the panels of specialists.
- None of the above
- Other (Specify)

II.2 Aspects of the ex post procedure

II.2.1 Institutional communication of evaluation results

25. Are the evaluation results public and accessible?

- Yes
- No

26. If you answered Yes to Question 25, which part of evaluation information is made public and accessible?

(Check all that apply)

- The number of research proposals submitted
- The level and degree of compliance with the terms and conditions of the call for proposals
- A detailed description of the criteria used for the evaluation of the research proposals and for the final selection of the research proposals to be funded.
- A description of the reviewers of the research proposals (number, country of residence, gender, disciplinary fields of action, level of training, etc.).
- A description of the members of the panels of specialists (number, country of residence, gender, disciplinary fields and areas of practice, level of training, etc.).
- The minimum, maximum and average number of evaluations for each research proposal.
- The total amounts funded by disciplinary fields and development problems to be addressed.
- A complete list of the research proposals selected for funding (including their titles, those responsible for them and their institutional affiliation, the development problems they address, the disciplinary fields and non-academic actors involved, and the resources allocated).
- The complete list of the research proposals (funded and unfunded, including their titles, the persons responsible for them and their institutional affiliation, the development problems they address, the disciplinary fields and non-academic actors involved, and the resources allocated).
- Other (Specify)

II.2.2 Personalized return of evaluation results

27. Do people responsible for the proposals submitted to the instrument receive a personalized feedback or evaluation report on their proposal?

- Yes
- No, research proposal sponsors receive a notification indicating whether or not their research proposal was selected for funding.

28. If you answered Yes to Question 27. Assuming that customized returns in addition to informing whether or not the proposal was funded and providing detailed suggestions that contribute to overcoming its major weaknesses, which of the following statements best represents the characteristics that such a report has? (Check the appropriate option)

- Does not include evaluations made by reviewers
- Includes all the evaluations made by the reviewers
- Includes an overall judgement made by the panels of specialists
- Includes all the evaluations made by the reviewers and an overall judgment made by the panels of specialists
- Other (specify)

II.2.3 Informational inputs and their emphasis for the evaluation

29. What informational inputs does your organization require for the evaluation of targeted research proposals? For each option, please indicate the importance of each informational input in the evaluation.

In this questionnaire "counterparts" refers to the non-academic actors associated or partners of the research proposals.

	Very important	Moderately important	Less important	No importance	Don't know
Research proposal	<input type="radio"/>				
CVs of those responsible for the proposals	<input type="radio"/>				
CVs of research team members	<input type="radio"/>				
Quantitative indicators (number of: peer-reviewed publications, publications in high impact journals, highly cited publications, citations, H-index, funded projects, patents, etc.) of those in charge of the proposals	<input type="radio"/>				
Quantitative indicators (number of: refereed publications, publications in high impact journals, highly cited publications, citations, H-index, funded projects, patents, etc.) of the research team members.	<input type="radio"/>				

	Very important	Moderately important	Less important	No importance	Don't know
Quantitative indicators of refereed publications of local/regional circulation of those responsible for the proposals.	<input type="radio"/>				
Quantitative indicators of refereed publications of local/regional circulation of the members of the research team.	<input type="radio"/>				
Written commitment that the data generated in the framework of the proposal and the research results obtained will be open access.	<input type="radio"/>				
Letters of interest in research results from counterparts involved in research proposals	<input type="radio"/>				
Interviews with the counterparts involved in the research proposals about their interest, their characteristics and the commitments they assume in carrying out the proposals.	<input type="radio"/>				
Evaluation reports by reviewers	<input type="radio"/>				
A statement of impact/application/societal benefits	<input type="radio"/>				

II.2.4 Competence level

30. What is the ratio of funded proposals to proposals submitted? (Check the option that most closely matches)

- Up to 25%
- More than 25% up to 50%
- More than 50% up to 75%
- More than 75% up to 100%

III. Evaluation Criteria

III.1 To assess the ability of the targeted research proposal to meet the program's/call's/scheme's objectives

31. What aspects does your organization require reviewers and/or panels of specialists to evaluate in order to assess the ability of the targeted research proposal to meet the objectives of the instrument? For each option indicate the importance of each aspect in the overall assessment.

	Very Important	Moderately importante	Less important	No importance	Don't Know
The importance of the problem or need to the stakeholders interested in the solution.	<input type="radio"/>				
The strength of the justification for the need for original research to solve the proposed problem.	<input type="radio"/>				
The concordance between the problem posed and the expectations expressed by the counterparts.	<input type="radio"/>				
The involvement of relevant actors from the governmental, productive or social sector linked to the problem to be addressed.	<input type="radio"/>				
The formation of inter-institutional teams that contribute to the exploration and implementation of the solutions to be found.	<input type="radio"/>				
The formation of multidisciplinary research teams, composed of the disciplinary fields necessary to comprehensively address the selected problem and the exploration of solutions.	<input type="radio"/>				

	Very Important	Moderately importante	Less important	No importance	Don't Know
The relevance of the proposed research in terms of its contribution to possible solutions.	<input type="radio"/>				
The relevance of the expected research results for the stakeholders involved.	<input type="radio"/>				
Potential economic and social impact of the research results.	<input type="radio"/>				
Potential contribution of the research proposal to public policies	<input type="radio"/>				
Potential contribution of the research proposal to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), grand challenges or other mission-driven initiatives.	<input type="radio"/>				
The planning of strategies aimed at the application of research results/implementation of solutions in collaboration with participating partners.	<input type="radio"/>				
The willingness and ability of partners to facilitate the implementation of solutions.	<input type="radio"/>				
Feasibility of the implementation of the results to be obtained	<input type="radio"/>				
The clarity of the proposal on the conditions necessary for the implementation of the results to be obtained.	<input type="radio"/>				

	Very Important	Moderately importante	Less important	No importance	Don't Know
The adequacy of the identification of the set of non-academic actors that should be involved in the implementation of the results to be obtained and the feasibility of the strategies to make their participation (including the population affected by the problem) viable in the implementation of the results to be obtained.	<input type="radio"/>				
Adequacy of the mechanisms for the transfer and appropriation of the results to be obtained by the interested counterparts.	<input type="radio"/>				
Clarity in the delimitation of the population that would benefit from the implementation of the research results	<input type="radio"/>				
Specific characteristics of the counterparts involved in the proposal as potential co-financiers and/or co-producers of knowledge.	<input type="radio"/>				

III.2 To assess the academic merits of proposals for targeted research

32. What aspects does your organization require reviewers and/or panels of specialists to evaluate in order to assess the academic merit of proposals for targeted research? For each option, please indicate the importance of each aspect in the overall evaluation.

	Very important	Moderately important	Less important	No importance	Don't know
Clarity of the description of the problem to study	<input type="radio"/>				
Accuracy and agreement of the objectives, questions and hypotheses / propositions	<input type="radio"/>				

	Very important	Moderately important	Less important	No importance	Don't know
Strength of the rationale for the research raised	<input type="radio"/>				
Conceptual relevance or academic interest of the problems to be addressed	<input type="radio"/>				
Originality of the expected results or solutions to be explored at the national / local level	<input type="radio"/>				
Originality of the expected results or solutions to be explored in the international arena	<input type="radio"/>				
Adequacy of the research design, methods and techniques to meet the objectives set	<input type="radio"/>				
Adequacy and updating of the bibliography	<input type="radio"/>				
If the composition of the research team brings together the disciplinary fields necessary to comprehensively address the selected problem and explore solutions	<input type="radio"/>				
Feasibility of the investigation in relation to knowledge and experience of those responsible for the proposal	<input type="radio"/>				
Feasibility of the investigation in relation to the concordance between the allocation of resources, the objectives, expected results and schedule of activities	<input type="radio"/>				

	Very important	Moderately important	Less important	No importance	Don't know
Systematic of the interactions foreseen with the counterparts involved during the development of the project	<input type="radio"/>				
Expected impact of the results in terms of solving the problems raised	<input type="radio"/>				
The generation of training spaces (undergraduate and graduate) and the development of research experiences for young people within the framework of the proposal, including the preparation of graduate and postgraduate theses	<input type="radio"/>				
The relevance and scope of the dissemination strategies of research results	<input type="radio"/>				

III.3 Policy adjustments to mitigate potential biases in the selection process of research proposals aimed at funding

33. Has your organization made any of the following policy adjustments to address any possible bias and / or discrimination observed in the selection process of research proposals for funding? (Check all that apply)

	whose non-academic counterparts have had little or no link with academic actors	who are linked with counterparts, whose access to research is difficult	that are located and / or are linked with counterparts located in peripheral areas	that ensure the diversity of disciplines and fields of knowledge (facilitating interdiscipline)	that ensure the greatest diversity of problems addressed (social and productive)	that ensure gender balance (minimum 50% parity)	other (based on ethnicity/ caste, región/periphery etc.)
Always they are of high quality, give priority to funding proposals...	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Introduction of quotas to balance the funding of proposals ...	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
No adjustments derived from institutional criteria of research policies are introduced in the selection process of proposals to be financed	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

34. Is there another policy adjustment not considered before? Which one?

35. Is there any other aspect that you consider important to report that was not covered in this questionnaire?

36. We would be grateful if you could complete the following contact information:

Full name:

Position held in the organization:

E-mail:

Telephone:

Cell phone:

37. Would you be interested in being part of an interview or answering follow-up questions from the research team?

Yes

No

Thank you very much for your valuable collaboration